

Chemical evaluation of contaminated soils for fluoride, phosphate and nitrate contents^ψ

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Manuscript received 28 July 2003, revised 9 March 2004, accepted 11 May 2004

Soil samples collected from different sites within the industrial areas of Jodhpur were analysed for the contents of fluoride, phosphate and nitrate using spectrophotometric method.

The unbridled growth of a number of small scale industries mainly of dyeing, printing, metal and minerals is posing industrial pollution in western Rajasthan. The waste water flushing out from these industries flows in open drains and finally emerges in a nearby river¹. This all raises the risk of affecting the quality of soils of this area due to percolation of the hazardous substances of waste water through the porous soil of land to soil horizons. Further the excessive use of fertilizers to enhance crop yields has deepened the problem of soil contamination. Thus, it is quite significant to have an overall analysis of soil for its major components, i.e. exchangeable cations, inorganic nonmetallic constituents and trace elements. However, in the present work, attention has been focussed on fluoride, phosphate and nitrate ions.

The authors have made a systematic determination of fluoride, phosphate and nitrate in soils of arid region of Jodhpur. Spectrophotometric method was preferred over colorimetry where common metal ions such as aluminium, iron and manganese, cause interference during determination and thus require preliminary distillation².

Results and discussion

Sample preparation : Saturated soil paste was prepared by adding distilled water to the sample of soil while stirring with a spatula. Soil water mixture was consolidated from time to time by tapping the sample container. At saturation, the soil paste slides freely and cleanly off the spatula³.

Calibration curves : A series of standards of fluoride, phosphate and nitrate were prepared to draw calibration curves between concentration and absorption.

Procedure : In prepared samples of soil, fluoride was determined by alizarin-zirconyl method⁴, where fluoride reacted with acid-zirconium-alizarin reagent to produce red

color with a λ_{max} at 540 nm. Phosphate reacts with ammonium molybdate under acidic conditions to form a heteropoly acid, molybdophosphoric acid. In the presence of vanadium, yellow vanadomolybdophosphoric acid is formed which is measurable at 440 nm⁵. The concentration of nitrate was quantified by noting the absorbance at 220 nm using UV-Vis spectrophotometry⁶.

The results of F⁻, PO₄³⁻ and NO₃⁻ determination in soils are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. Spectrophotometric determination of fluoride, phosphate and nitrate in soil samples

Sample site	N	Concentration (ppm)*		
		F ⁻	PO ₄ ³⁻	NO ₃ ⁻
1	7	ND	45.0	73.5
2	6	ND	23.0	106.3
3	8	ND	38.9	151.1
4	8	0.45	30.0	77.0
5	7	ND	39.0	83.7
6	8	0.56	27.0	149.7
7	6	1.71	84.0	103.5
8	6	1.25	34.5	63.5
9	8	ND	26.7	76.7
Total samples	64 (±)	SD 0.09	1.10	0.66

*Average value of three determinations.

N = Number of samples collected from the site.

SD = Standard deviation.

Experimental

Instrumentation : A C-160-MK-II spectrochem spectrophotometer of Amil was used to measure absorbance of fluoride and phosphate. It is a single beam grating spectrophotometer having a standard light source of tungsten filament lamp.

^ψPart of Ph.D. Thesis Ratna Rajpal.

A Systronics-119 UV-Vis spectrophotometer was used for the estimation of nitrate. A 1200 grooves/nm halographic grating with czerney-turner mount and sufficiently long focal length optics with narrow slits ensures a 3 nm spectral bands width throughout the range. Deuterium lamp and tungsten-halogen lamp are attached for light source.

Sample collection : Samples of soil were collected from different sites of Marudhar and Basni Industrial Areas of Jodhpur. All in all nine sites were selected from where a total of 64 soil samples were obtained for analysis as given in Table 1. To ensure a representative sample of soil from a site, six small samples were collected within a ten meter radius and mixed thoroughly. These were taken in polyethylene bags using a stainless steel tube sampler of 5 cm diameter to enable soil removal upto a depth of atleast 5 cm. A minimum mass of 50 g was collected from each sampling point⁷.

A.R. grade chemicals were used. All stock solutions were prepared in double-distilled water. Zirconium-alizarin reagent for fluoride and a solution containing ammonium molybdate and ammonium metavanadate (vanadate-molybdate reagent) for phosphate were prepared as described elsewhere⁸.

Conclusion :

The disposal of industrial waste is the major problem responsible for soil contamination. Being a key component of environmental cycle soil is receptor of huge quantities of harmful materials. Atmospheric nitrogen oxides are con-

verted to nitrates which are eventually deposited on soil. Much of the sulphur dioxide emitted from burning of fuels ends up on soil as sulphate. The complete analysis of soil is thus required to evaluate the quality of soil for its agricultural value. The present studies are of paramount importance as Jodhpur lies in Thar desert belt and often experiences very limited resources of food production.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for financial assistance [Project No. F-12-2/2001 (SR-I)].

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